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TNFRSF10C (DcR1) activation by HPV16 E7.

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We measured total transcription in primary foreskin keratinocytes following engineered ectopic expression of the E7 oncoprotein. We describe here activation of *Tnfrsf10c* by HPV16 E7.

Citations

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